

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Yield of rice-fish cultivation at Cuttack, India

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We explored the prospects of aquaculture by controlled breeding and short-term (4½ mo) seed-rearing of air-breathing clariid catfish *Clarias batrachus* in renovated fields cropped with high-yielding rice cultivar CR1018 (Pankaj/Jagannath).

The experiment consisted of a control plot of rice alone and plots of rice with fish. The plots were 0.05 ha each and had a gradient of 1.80%. A 10% area was excavated at the lower end of each rice-fish plot for a fish-shelter pit. Farmyard manure (5 t/ha) was applied to all plots during land preparation. A basal application of 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha was incorporated before direct seeding rice the first week

Compatibility of rice cultivar CR1018 with air-breathing clariid catfish at CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Item	Rice alone	Rice + fish
Grain yield (t)	4.1	3.1
Fish yield (t)	—	0.4
Grain value (\$)	440.40	400.3 ^a
Fish value (\$)	—	361.9 ^b
Total value (\$)	440.4	768.2
<i>Additional costs (\$) to raise fish crop/ha</i>		
Land preparation		32.8
20 g/160 brood fish		32.8
1 t fish offal		free ^c
1 t cow dung		2.9
Harvesting		12.3

^aSale price is \$108/t on farm. ^bSale price is \$1/kg on farm. ^cCollected from fish market.

of Jun 1985. Standard cultivation practices were followed.

One month after sowing, four male and four female catfish were released in each plot. To encourage breeding, a few round earthen pots were embedded in the soil at the periphery of the plots. The spawners bred profusely 10-15 d from release. The fish spawns were fed daily with low-cost feed — minced fish offal and raw cow dung. Fish were harvested with

rice in late Nov 1985. Plots were slowly drained, allowing the fish to move to the pits where they could be collected by drag-netting and hand.

Rice production was about the same in both treatments (see table). Growing clariid catfish with rice under intermediate rained lowland conditions, with provision of the fish-shelter pit, could boost farm returns 55.4% over rice monocropping. □

A rice - grain legume cropping system

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Rice farmers of Kerala find cultivating grain legumes during the rice fallow season a promising technology to augment their family incomes. To identify a viable rice - grain legume cropping system for rice fallows, we studied four grain legumes (greengram *Vigna radiata*, blackgram *Vigna mungo*, cowpea *Vigna unguiculata*, and redgram *Cajanus cajan*) and two cropping systems: relay (sowing

legume in standing crop of rice) and sequential (sowing legumes soon after harvest of rice) during kharif and rabi, 1985-86.

Soil was a sandy loam (pH 5.07, organic C, 1.6%; Bray's available P, 47 kg/ha; and exchangeable K, 248 kg/ha). The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Treatments were factorial combinations of grain legumes and cropping systems.

Triveni rice was transplanted on 6 Aug 1985 at 15 × 10 cm spacing and fertilized with 70-15-29 kg NPK/ha. Harvest was on 27 Oct 1985. Grain legume seeds were dibbled on 19 Oct in relay cropping and on 28 Oct in

sequential cropping. Redgram was dibbled at 30 × 20 cm spacing and other legumes at 30 × 15 cm. Fertilizer for the legumes was 20-13-17 kg NPK/ha, half N and full P and K basally and the remaining N as a combined foliar spray of 2% urea and 0.1% phosphamidon 100 EC at 25 d after dibbling. The rabi legumes were raised without tillage and irrigation.

The main effects of grain legumes and cropping systems are presented in Table 1, and the interaction effects in Table 2. Legume grain yield showed a significant interaction of legume and cropping system. Blackgram relay-cropped with rice produced significantly high grain yield (0.92

Table 1. Yields of kharif rice and rabi grain legumes by cropping system.^a Kerala, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Rice grain yield (t/ha)	Legume						
		Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain-to-straw ratio	Threshing percentage	Pod length (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant ht (cm)
Grain legume varieties								
Greengram ML-5	2.3	0.05	0.25	0.21	52	6.1	38	26.2
Blackgram PDU-3	2.3	0.71	0.86	0.82	63	5.3	38	30.9
Cowpea PTB-1	2.3	0.48	1.25	0.38	69	16.9	45	46.8
Redgram DA-9	2.5	0.19	0.44	0.43	41	4.6	61	36.2
CD (5%)	ns	0.10	0.22	—	3.3	0.4	0.8	3.4
Cropping systems								
Relay cropping	2.3	0.42	0.69	0.61	55	8.8	46	36.7
Sequential cropping	2.4	0.30	0.71	0.42	58	7.6	46	33.3
CD (5%)	ns	0.07	ns	—	2.3	0.3	ns	2.4

^a ns = not significant.

t/ha). Yields of blackgram after rice (0.49 t/ha), cowpea after rice (0.49 t/ha), and cowpea relayed with rice (0.47 t/ha) were statistically equal. All other combinations produced very low yields.

Grain-to-straw ratios were maximum for blackgram and for relay cropping. Other crop attributes — threshing percentage, pod length, days to 50% flowering, and plant height — also were significantly influenced by the interaction of legume species with cropping systems.

Results indicate that kharif rice with a relay-planted rabi blackgram may be a promising rice - grain legume cropping system. □

Table 2. Grain legumes and cropping systems effects on grain yield and ancillary characters of rabi grain legumes. Kerala, India, 1985-86.

Cropping system and character	Grain legume				CD (5%)
	Greengram	Blackgram	Cowpea	Redgram	
Grain yield (t/ha)					
Relay cropping	0.05	0.92	0.47	0.24	0.15
Sequential cropping	0.06	0.49	0.49	0.14	
Threshing percentage					
Relay cropping	43	66	70	40	4.6
Sequential cropping	62	59	68	42	
Pod length (cm)					
Relay cropping	6.4	5.9	18.0	4.7	0.50
Sequential cropping	5.8	4.6	15.7	4.5	
50% flowering (d)					
Relay cropping	40	40	45	59	1.2
Sequential cropping	37	36	46	63	
Plant height (cm)					
Relay cropping	28.2	35.0	48.6	35.1	4.8
Sequential cropping	24.2	26.8	45.0	37.3	

Announcements

International Hybrid Rice Symposium Recommendations

About 220 delegates and observers from 17 countries and IRRI attended the First International Symposium on Hybrid Rice, Changsha, China, 6-10 October 1986.

Delegates reviewed the status of hybrid rice in China, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, Malaysia, Mexico, Republic of Korea, and the United States and discussed the prospects for hybrid rice production in Asia and the Pacific Region.

Three task forces recommended target environments for hybrid rice, directions of future research, and mechanisms for collaborative research. Irrigated and favorable rainfed areas are the most likely target environments for hybrid rice development because yields are already high, infrastructure to aid hybrid seed production is well developed, and farmers in those areas can more likely meet the cost of hybrid seed purchases each crop season.

Research priorities identified were methods of hybrid development, raising the level of heterosis,

developing cultural practices for growing hybrids, and the economics of hybrid rice production. Asexual seed production is considered the most important long-term breeding goal.

Because hybrid rice programs outside China are in their infancy, the task force on collaboration recommended that an international network on hybrid rice be established and that individual countries establish national programs and mechanisms for network participation. □